

Condensation of *m*-Halogeno-anisoles with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid in presence of Sulphuric Acid

K. A. Thakar

m-Halogeno-anisoles have been condensed with acetone dicarboxylic acid. Halogen and methoxyl group being *ortho-para* orienting, the condensation is therefore likely to take place at 2, 4, or 6 position.

The products have been found identical with the corresponding β -(2-methoxy-4-halogenophenyl)glutaconic acids, obtained by simultaneous hydrolysis and methylation of 7-halogeno-coumarin-4-acetic acids.

Acetone dicarboxylic acid condenses with anisole in the *para* position with the formation of β -(4-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic acid¹. The isomeric β -(2-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic acid² was obtained from coumarin-4-acetic acid by subjecting it to the successive action of alkali and methylation.

This communication deals with the condensation of *m*-halogeno-anisoles with acetone dicarboxylic acid in presence of sulphuric acid. The condensation products are identical with the products obtained by the simultaneous hydrolysis and methylation of 7-halogeno-coumarin-4-acetic acids³. This conclusively proves that the condensation takes place in the *ortho* position with respect to the methoxyl and *para* position with respect to the halogen groups with the formation of β -(2-methoxy-4-halogenophenyl)glutaconic acids.

This seems to be in keeping with the fact that hydroxyl group is *ortho*-orienting and halogen groups are *para*-orienting.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -(2-Methoxy-4-chlorophenyl)glutaconic Acid (III: X=Cl): (a). By Hydrolysis of 7-Chlorocoumarin-4-acetic Acid.—7-Chlorocoumarin-4-acetic acid (II: X = Cl) was simultaneously hydrolysed and methylated⁴. The reaction product on acidification was poured into water. The solid formed was repeatedly crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p.

1. Limaye and Bhavs, *this Journal*, 1931, 8, 137.
2. Limaye, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1932, Part III, p. 236.
3. Thakar, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 397.
4. Canter and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 187.

162° (decomp.). [Found: C, 53.20; H, 4.08; equiv., 136.9. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires C, 53.23; H, 4.07%; equiv., 135.25 (dibasic acid)].

(b). *By Condensation of m-Chloro-anisole with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid.*—*m*-Chloro-anisole (18 g.) was added to a mixture of acetone dicarboxylic acid and H_2SO_4 (conc.), prepared from citric acid (70 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 130ml). The liquid mixture was stirred at 10° for 3 hours. It was kept overnight and then refluxed at 50° for 4 hours. The reaction mass was poured over crushed ice. The solid formed was crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 162° (decomp.), yield 3%. Mixed m.p. of this compound with β -(2-methoxy-4-chlorophenyl)glutaconic acid (III: X = Cl), prepared above, showed no depression.

Hydroxy Anhydride of β -(2-Methoxy-4-chlorophenyl)glutaconic Acid.— β -(2-Methoxy-4-chlorophenyl)glutaconic acid (1 g.) was either heated above its m.p. or heated with acetic anhydride for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene in fine needles, m.p. 115°. It developed a reddish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 56.98; H, 3.45. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl$ requires C, 57.03; H, 3.56%).

β -(2-Methoxy-4-bromophenyl)glutaconic Acid (III, X = Br): (a). *By Hydrolysis of 7-Bromocoumarin-4-acetic Acid.*—7-Bromocoumarin-4-acetic acid (II: X = Br) was simultaneously hydrolysed and methylated as its chloro isomer. It was crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 172° (decomp.). (Found: C, 45.40; H, 3.41; equiv., 158.2. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Br$ requires C, 45.72; H, 3.49%; equiv., 157.5).

(b). *By Condensation of m-Bromo-anisole with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid.*—*m*-Bromo-anisole (25 g.) was added to a mixture of acetone dicarboxylic acid. The liquid mixture was treated further as its chloro isomer. It was crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 172° (decomp.). Mixed m.p. with β -(2-methoxy-4-bromophenyl)glutaconic acid showed no depression.

Hydroxy Anhydride of β -(2-Methoxy-4-bromophenyl)glutaconic acid was prepared as its chloro isomer and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 125°. It showed a reddish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 48.32; H, 3.04. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 48.49; H, 3.03%).

β -(4-Iodo-2-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic Acid (III: X = I): (a). *By Hydrolysis and Methylation of 7-Iodocoumarin-4-acetic Acid.*—7-Iodocoumarin-4-acetic acid (II: X = I) was simultaneously hydrolysed and methylated like its chloro isomer. The solid formed was repeatedly crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 196° (decomp.). (Found: C, 39.52; H, 3.04; equiv., 182.60. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3I$ requires C, 39.78; H, 3.04%; equiv., 181.00).

(b). *By Condensation of m-Iodo-anisole with Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid.*—*m*-Iodo-anisole (30.9 g.) was treated with acetone dicarboxylic acid and the liquid mixture was treated as its chloro isomer. The precipitated solid was crystallised from 30% acetic acid, m.p. 196° (decomp.). Mixed m.p. with the acid obtained by hydrolysis and methylation of 7-iodocoumarin-4-acetic acid showed no depression.

Hydroxy Anhydride of β -(4-Iodo-2-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic Acid.— β -(4-Iodo-2-methoxyphenyl)glutaconic acid was heated above its m.p. like its chloro isomer. The solid formed was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 130°. It developed a reddish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 41.66; H, 2.49. $C_{12}H_9O_4I$ requires C, 41.86; H, 2.62%).

Author's sincere thanks are due to Dr. R. C. Shah for the help received from him.